

**STUDY ON SYNTHESIS AND COMPREHENSIVE
CHARACTERIZATION OF METAL OXIDE AND
REDUCED GRAPHENE OXIDE BASED
NANOCOMPOSITE FOR GAS SENSING APPLICATION**

A Thesis

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Synopsis

Introduction

A gas sensor is a sensor that senses the presence of gases in its vicinity for a range of distance and is used as a safety system. Gas sensors are designed in a view of detecting the leakage of gases and other emissions which will be helpful in automatically shutting down the leakage immediately. These sensors are connected with alerting systems such as alarms which sounds upon detecting the toxic gases and can save human and animal life. Gas sensors are applicable in knowing the presence of combustible, flammable and toxic gases, and can also provide the number of gases present in a specific area. These sensors are often used in industries, mines, firefighting, leakage detection and emission detection.

Detecting gas leakage is a route to recognize toxic gases using a detector i.e., the sensor. The audible alarms embedded in these sensor systems help people to move away from the dangerous zone attentively to a safe place. The possible causes of toxic gas exposures are painting, fumigation, fuel filling, construction, excavation of contaminated soils, landfill operations, entering confined spaces, etc. Gas sensors are of different types depending on their operating principle. Combustible gas sensors, photoionization detectors, infrared point sensors, ultrasonic sensors, electrochemical gas sensors, and semiconductor sensors are some of the gas sensors in use. All these types of sensors are widely used in applications in industrial plants, refineries, pharmaceutical manufacturing, sterilization facilities, paper pulp mills, aircraft and shipbuilding facilities, wastewater treatment facilities, automobiles, indoor air quality testing and homes.

In recent times, for forecasting global climate changes diverse climate models have been used extensively. When greenhouse gases like carbon dioxide (CO_2) surges in the atmosphere, resultant in increasing temperature connected to the surface of the earth as well as in the troposphere. The discharge of CO_2 in the atmosphere affects human health by displacing oxygen. Due to the rise in the level of CO_2 breathing becomes tougher for mankind.

CO_2 can lead to cause headaches and health complaints in closed zones. It is necessary to constantly check the amount of CO_2 being released into the atmosphere through various means like efficient combustion of fossil fuels in vehicles, burning of coal in thermal power plants. Carbon dioxide poisoning constitutes additionally a severe threat to prominent people cautiously working in confined places like key industries and independent labs. Therefore, it is significant to produce economically cheap, fast and reliable CO_2 sensors for sensing and monitoring regularly. Many necessary materials have

been used as sensing element like metallic oxides, polymer-based sensors, electrolyte sensors, etc. in sophisticated CO₂ sensors. Sensors scientifically based on metallic sensing elements frequently require high-temperature processes for modern fabrication. This can be prevented by employing polymer-based sensing elements and also, they can be utilized to detect a vast range of analytes. Metal oxide nanocomposites allow a broad scope in gas sensing application.

In this research work, CO₂ gas sensors were developed by metal oxides like Cerium oxide (CeO₂) and Chromium oxide (Cr₂O₃) also with the combination of reduced graphene oxide & metal oxides. Metal oxide and reduced graphene oxide were homogenized with Polyethyleneimine solution and coated on the interdigitated electrode (IDE) prepared from copper-clad to sense CO₂ gas based on resistance change. Physisorption between CO₂ & metal oxide – rGO at room temperature is the primary sensing mechanism for detecting CO₂. All sensors (0.25, 0.50, 0.75 & 1.00 wt %) could accurately detect 200 – 1000 ppm CO₂ gas.

Objectives

The main aims of the present work are furnished below.

- Synthesis of metal oxides by wet chemical methods.
- Preparation of IDE (Interdigitated electrode) by copper-clad to function as the substrate.
- Preparation of metal oxide and reduced graphene nanocomposite solution and coating on IDE to fabricate sensor.
- Comprehensive characterization of synthesized metal oxides and prepared metal oxide and reduced graphene oxide nanocomposite sensors.
- Experimental methods to qualify the metal oxide and reduced graphene nanocomposite for gas sensing application.
- Interpretation of results, evolving relation among the properties investigated and publication in reviewed journals.

Experimental Procedures and details

PEI – rGO nanocomposite for CO₂ sensing application

In this work, PEI & synthesised rGO materials were selected with varied weight percentage for sensing CO₂ gas at room temperature. Furthermore, PEI – rGO composite

film of varied rGO concentration was fabricated by drop-casting the sensitive films on IDEs. The IDEs were made effectively by copper clads. Response capabilities of all the four sensors to CO₂ at room temperature were examined. It was observed that all four sensor devices follow similar trends in their response to CO₂. Resistance over CO₂ concentration decreases gradually with an increase in rGO weight percentage. In addition to this, the sensitivity of the sensors increases gradually with the concentration of CO₂ up to 1000 ppm. The sensors showed excellent repeatability with no corresponding change in values for specific periods through the cycles. Furthermore, the sensor with 0.25 wt % records a very fast response and recovery time and a considerable time delay is observed for 1 wt % of PEI - rGO.

PEI – CeO₂ nanocomposite for CO₂ sensing application

In this work, the relevant materials were wisely adopted for sensing CO₂ efficiently were PEI & CeO₂ with differing weight percentage at room temperature. Furthermore, PEI – CeO₂ composite film of varied RGO concentration was produced by drop-casting the sensitive films on IDEs. The IDEs were consistently made by copper clads. FESEM and EDAX analysis show the agglomerated CeO₂ nano-particles and spectra owing to the high purity of the CeO₂ synthesized. UV-Visible spectra exhibit a strong absorption band at 322.4 nm wavelength which corresponds to UV range, affirms the effective synthesis of CeO₂ nanoparticles. XRD studies show crystalline nature and the prominent peaks correspond to the successful synthesis of CeO₂ nanoparticles. Response capabilities of all the four sensors to CO₂ at room temperature were effectively investigated. It was perceived thoughtfully that all four sensors devices typically follow homogeneous trends in their productive response to CO₂. Furthermore, exceptionally rapid response and recovery time were scientifically shown by the sensor with 0.25 wt % of CeO₂. These sensors can be essentially used to precisely detect CO₂ from a determined concentration of 1000 ppm and below. The sensors accurately showed magnificent repeatability with no corresponding change in individual values for definite periods through the cycles.

PEI – Cr₂O₃ nanocomposite for CO₂ sensing application

In this work, PEI & synthesised chromium oxide (Cr₂O₃) materials were selected with varied weight percentage for sensing CO₂ gas at room temperature. Furthermore, PEI – Cr₂O₃ composite film of varied Cr₂O₃ concentration was fabricated by drop-casting the sensitive films on IDEs. The IDEs were made effectively by copper clads. Response

capabilities of all the four sensors to CO₂ at room temperature were examined. It was observed that all four sensor devices follow similar trends in their response to CO₂. Resistance over CO₂ concentration decreases gradually with an increase in Cr₂O₃ weight percentage. In addition to this, the sensitivity of the sensors increases gradually with the concentration of CO₂ up to 1000 ppm. The sensors showed excellent repeatability with no corresponding change in values for specific periods through the cycles. Furthermore, the sensor with 0.25 wt % records a very fast response and recovery time and a considerable time delay is observed for 1 wt % of PEI - Cr₂O₃.

PEI – CeO₂ – rGO nanocomposite for CO₂ sensing application

In this work, PEI, synthesised cerium oxide (CeO₂) & rGO materials were selected with varied weight percentage for sensing CO₂ gas at room temperature. Furthermore, PEI – CeO₂ – rGO composite film of varied CeO₂ - rGO concentration was fabricated by drop-casting the sensitive films on IDEs. The IDEs were made effectively by copper clads. Response capabilities of all the four sensors to CO₂ at room temperature were examined. It was observed that all four sensor devices follow similar trends in their response to CO₂. Resistance over CO₂ concentration decreases gradually with an increase in CeO₂ - rGO weight percentage. In addition to this, the sensitivity of the sensors increases gradually with the concentration of CO₂ up to 1000 ppm. The sensors showed excellent repeatability with no corresponding change in values for specific periods through the cycles. Furthermore, the sensor with 0.25 wt % records a very fast response and recovery time and a considerable time delay is observed for 1 wt % of PEI - CeO₂-rGO.

PEI – Cr₂O₃ – rGO nanocomposite for CO₂ sensing application

In this section, PEI, Cr₂O₃ & rGO materials were selected with varied weight percentage for sensing CO₂ gas at room temperature. Furthermore, PEI – Cr₂O₃ - rGO composite film of varied Cr₂O₃ - rGO concentration was fabricated by drop-casting the sensitive films on IDEs. The IDEs were made effectively by copper clads. Response capabilities of all the four sensors to CO₂ at room temperature were examined. It was observed that all four sensor devices follow similar trends in their response to CO₂. Resistance over CO₂ concentration decreases gradually with an increase in Cr₂O₃ - rGO weight percentage. In addition to this, the sensitivity of the sensors increases gradually with the concentration of CO₂ up to 1000 ppm. The sensors showed excellent repeatability with no corresponding change in values for specific periods through the

cycles. Furthermore, the sensor with 0.25 wt % records a very fast response and recovery time and a considerable time delay is observed for 1 wt % of PEI - Cr₂O₃ - rGO.

Structure of the Thesis

The thesis is divided into 9 chapters.

Chapter 1 deals with fundamental aspects of gas sensors and its requirement and the current status of gas sensors. Further, general features related to copper clad. The details on cerium oxide, chromium oxide and reduced graphene oxide are also discussed for gas sensing purpose.

Chapter 2 deals with a brief review of the literature about investigations on the gas sensors besides the effectiveness of metal oxide & reduced graphene oxide-based nanocomposite and other types of nanoparticles on CO₂ sensing is given.

Chapter 3 deals with the objectives of the current research work followed by the scope of the investigation are furnished.

Chapter 4 deals with materials, methods, experimental, characterization & results & discussions related to polyethyleneimine – reduced graphene oxide nanocomposite for CO₂ sensing application followed by analysis and correlation of the sensitivity properties for various formulations with the analysis results.

Chapter 5 deals with materials, methods, experimental, characterization & results and discussions related to polyethyleneimine – cerium oxide nanocomposite for CO₂ sensing application followed by analysis and correlation of the sensitivity properties for various formulations with the analysis results.

Chapter 6 deals with materials, methods, experimental, characterization & results and discussions related to Polyethyleneimine – Chromium oxide nanocomposite for CO₂ sensing application followed by analysis and correlation of the sensitivity properties for various formulations with the analysis results.

Chapter 7 deals with materials, methods, experimental, characterization & results and discussions related to Polyethyleneimine – Cerium oxide – Reduced graphene oxide nanocomposite for CO₂ sensing application followed by analysis and correlation of the sensitivity properties for various formulations with the analysis results.

Chapter 8 deals with materials, methods, experimental, characterization & results and discussions related to Polyethyleneimine – Chromium oxide – Reduced graphene

oxide nanocomposite for CO₂ sensing application followed by analysis and correlation of the sensitivity properties for various formulations with the analysis results.

Chapter 9 brings about the overall summary drawn from the present investigation work followed by future work that can be undertaken for further development in the formulation of composites and experimental processing resulting in increased CO₂ sensitivity.